

D6.2

Vulnerabilities in Europe During Times of Transition

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Disclaimer

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Abstract

This study develops a multidimensional framework to assess cumulative exposure to climate-related risks across Europe, integrating health, energy, transport, and socioeconomic conditions. By mapping risk distribution across regions and measuring dependence, we capture the interconnectedness of exposures and identify key socioeconomic drivers. Our findings reveal a substantial variation in risk distribution, with no clear geographical patterns. Unsurprisingly, household income emerges as the strongest determinant of exposure. We extend this analysis by projecting cumulative exposure to 2050, applying climate scenarios. The results suggest gradual rather than sharp change in exposure over time, with some areas exhibiting sharp rises; however, average risks are expected to rise across the entire continent.

1. Introduction

The protection of individuals from risks, whether economic, social, environmental, or health-related, has historically been a key driver in the formation of collective institutions. These institutions were established to pool resources, manage uncertainties, and provide social protection. Ensuring citizens' protection emerged both as a successful adaptive strategy and as a response to demands for greater equality. Europe itself, in the form of the Communities of Coal and Steel, was born as a tool to deflate the risk of internal conflict on the continent. Moreover, the treaties that form the foundation of the European Union include risk mitigation through mechanisms of solidarity among member states as a core objective. Both the treaties and the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union explicitly affirm that all European citizens have the right to protection from health, employment, and climate-related risks, as exemplified by the EU Civil Protection Mechanism.

This study explores climate-related risks in Europe from a multidimensional perspective, with a particular focus on cumulative exposure.¹ We map multiple risks across European regions by integrating information from various sources, focusing on risks related to climate change and the ongoing ecological transition.

In times of transition and climate crisis, climatic risks are expected to increase for many individuals across the continent. Climate change has indeed far-reaching impacts on ecosystems, economies, and societies worldwide (Stern, 2022; Bednar-Friedl et al., 2022). In response, achieving climate neutrality has become a top priority for the European Union, leading to a wide range of policy interventions (European Commission, 2020). However, as with any profound economic shift, multiple spillover effects arise from climate change itself and the policies designed to mitigate it. Ensuring that the most affected territories and population groups receive adequate protection is essential to preventing further inequalities in the transition toward a sustainable economic model.

Despite growing concerns over climate impacts, little is known about individuals who are simultaneously vulnerable across multiple socioeconomic dimensions or about the conditions that determine their exposure to climate-related changes. The existing literature has primarily focused on economy-wide or sector-specific costs of climate change, often quantified in terms of GDP or sectoral output (Dell et al., 2014; Burke et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2023), while broader distributive impacts on households remain understudied. Although recent research has examined climate change's effects on income inequality, these studies mostly focus on aggregate country-level assessments (Diffenbaugh and Burke, 2019; Palagi et al., 2022). While they demonstrate that climate change exacerbates inequalities within and between countries, they fail to identify the most affected individuals.

Some studies have analyzed climate change's impact on households, highlighting its micro-level consequences. Hallegatte and Rozenberg (2017) use a bottom-up approach to examine climate change's effects on poverty, showing that poor households can be disproportionately affected even when overall economic losses are moderate. Campagnolo et al. (2023) explore changes in income sources and expenditures among European households, finding heterogeneous effects across socioeconomic groups and regions. Beaussier, Chevalier, and Palier (2024) further reveal that while the poorest citizens are the most exposed and vulnerable to transition policies, the lower middle class is also significantly impacted by such measures. However, these approaches fail to capture

¹ As discussed below, we jointly considering the exposure to climate-related risks and vulnerability coming from different socioeconomic conditions and thus use cumulative exposure and cumulative vulnerability interchangeably.

the cumulative nature of climatic risks, leaving a critical gap in understanding how multiple intersecting risks shape individuals' overall risk exposure.

Building on the literature on inequality and concentration (Decancq, 2014; Decancq, 2020; García-Gómez, Pérez, and Prieto-Alaiz, 2021), we analyze the distribution of risks from a multidimensional perspective. Our framework explicitly recognizes that certain individuals are more likely to experience multiple overlapping risks, providing a comprehensive micro-level assessment of climate change's potential impacts. We consider exposure to four climate-related risks – energy and transport insecurity, reflecting climate-related demand shocks and rising energy costs, and health risks, particularly those related to respiratory and cardiovascular conditions – together with socioeconomic conditions, which account for three different vulnerabilities that can amplify the adverse effect of climatic risks. We integrate seven areas or dimensions of exposure and vulnerability to define overall risk.

We merge data from multiple sources to integrate all dimensions into a single dataset, enabling a comprehensive analysis of risk distribution across Europe. We assess exposure levels, identify dominant risk factors by region, and examine how socioeconomic factors drive variations within countries. Additionally, we analyze inequality in risk distribution to pinpoint areas where exposure is concentrated among specific population groups. Beyond mapping risks, we capture the interconnectedness of risks by measuring dependence at the regional level. Our dependence measure highlights whether individuals are affected -or not- by several risks at the same time, emphasizing the cumulative dimension of exposure.

Given the forward-looking nature of climate change, we also project cumulative exposure around 2050, identifying emerging regional patterns under different future scenarios. Following Campagnolo et al. (2023), we estimate historical statistical relationships between climate-related hazards and risks and apply these estimates to future climate and socioeconomic scenarios. Using the standard scenario framework (O'Neill et al., 2016), we consider both a moderate and a severe climate change scenario.

While previous research has largely examined risks in isolation, this study provides new insights into cumulative exposures. Cardiovascular risks are the most prevalent across Europe, particularly in the East, significantly contributing to overall exposure. Energy poverty is another major concern, especially in Southern and Eastern regions. Risk distribution varies considerably: some Mediterranean regions (e.g., southern Spain, Greece, Cyprus) exhibit high inequality and dependence, while parts of Central Europe (Germany, Poland, Czech Republic) and Italy show lower levels. Household income emerges as the primary predictor of average risk, except in Italy and the Czech Republic, where age plays a greater role. When classifying the population in each country into risk groups, we observe substantial variation within countries. In fact, after partitioning the population into groups based on expected risk and decomposing total risk variance into within-country and between-country components, the latter accounts for just over 10%. Notably, we observe groups exposed to substantial risk even in countries with very low average risk.

Moreover, we demonstrate no clear regional patterns at continental level, with gradual projected changes in exposure. Still, the effects in relative terms are worryingly noteworthy in some areas, where the population suffering from energy and transport poverty is projected to even double. Overall, average risk is expected to increase in both scenarios, particularly under the severe climate change future. We believe our findings highlight the need for country-specific analyses, based on more granular data, to better understand and address climate-related risks.

The paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature and discusses the dimensions through which climate change can affect individuals. Section 3 presents the empirical approach, including the measurement of each dimension, the matching exercise, the future climatic and risks

projections and the estimation of cumulative exposure. Section 4 describes the data. Section 5 presents the results coming from the individual and regional analysis. Section 6 concludes.

2. Related literature

2.1 Climate change and vulnerable groups

In recent years, the world has gone through major events including the COVID-19 pandemic, the return of war to Europe and escalating climate change-induced extreme weather conditions. The emerging risks associated with these developments challenge their perception and quantification due to their long-term consequences and uncertain evolution. A systematic risk assessment would help identify groups most vulnerable to future shocks. In this regard, Palencia-Esteban and Valentini (2025) review the key risks and shocks expected in Europe in the coming decades.

The reports published to date agree that climate and environmental risks will dominate over the next decade (among others, EC, 2021; WEF, 2023; EPRS-IPOL-EXPO, 2023; EEA, 2024). Townend, Aylett and Benzie (2023) have explored the overarching impact of cascading climate, showing how different types of climate triggers and transmission mechanisms can affect European societies. This point is stressed by Palencia-Esteban and Valentini (2025), who created a map of climate change risk interconnections. Besides highlighting the more direct negative consequences of climate change, they emphasize the interconnected nature of these impacts, showcasing the complex and widespread effects across multiple areas.

Translating the cost of climate change at the household or individual level and identifying the most vulnerable socioeconomic groups to climate related risks is not straightforward. As Campagnolo et al. (2023) remark, most economic impact assessments have focused on economy-wide or sector-wide costs related to specific climate change impacts, adaptation responses or mitigation policies, without jointly quantifying all three dimensions. These assessments usually measure costs in terms of GDP or sectoral output changes, often overlooking the overall and distributive impacts on households (Dell et al., 2014; Burke et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2023).

Although a growing body of research has studied how climate change affects income inequality, its distributional impact is typically examined on a broad scale. Researchers often examine regional or national economies to evaluate how climate change affects various measures of inequality (Diffenbaugh and Burke 2019; Cappelli, Costantini and Consoli, 2021; Palagi et al., 2022; Cevic and Jalles, 2023). To the best of our knowledge, Hallegatte and Rozenberg (2017) were the first to address the micro-level consequences of climate change at the household level.

In this line, Campagnolo et al. (2023) have recently quantified the costs of climate change impacts and adaptation on European households through the expenditure, asset and productivity channels by exploring changes in expenditure patterns and income sources. Their future climate change cost projections reveal a North-South divide. Health, food and electricity expenditure are expected to remain constant in Northern and Eastern Europe, whereas these expenses will increase mostly in Southern countries. From a resource perspective, monetary incomes will be negatively affected in nearly all countries, excluding the Eastern regions, but the contraction in labor income outstands in the South. As shown, climate change would increase the population at risk of poverty, but poor households would be particularly vulnerable. Overall, the cost of climate change will be unequally

distributed across European subnational regions and socioeconomic groups, so it is vital for policy responses to take these considerations into account.

The literature has paid limited attention to the social risks that environmental transitions pose at the individual level, particularly those arising from mitigation and adaptation policies. There is still limited understanding of which population groups may be adversely affected by the policies designed to address climate change. Beaussier, Chevalier and Palier (2024) have questioned who is at risk from climate policies in France. Besides illustrating an exposure bias, where extreme events hit the poor harder, they also look at the distribution of brown jobs (as a proxy for job loss risk), patterns of car usage (first/second hand and fuel type) and housing characteristics (retrofitting and renovation costs), all of which are key targets of environmental policies. The poorest citizens are the most exposed and vulnerable to the direct impact of climate change, but the lower middle class also has much to lose from transition policies.

From a regional perspective, the projected effects of climate change on people, ecosystems and economies differ across regions in the EU (European Commission, 2024), risking an increase in regional inequalities. The most affected areas are concentrated in the Mediterranean region and in the eastern EU, who are already poorer than the average. Climate policies also have an uneven regional impact. The Regional Green Transition Vulnerability Index developed by Rodríguez-Pose and Bartalucci (2023), a composite measure capturing both the direct and indirect impacts, unmasks strong regional variations in this vulnerability. The less developed, peri-urban and rural regions in Southern and Eastern Europe appear more exposed to the expected changes steaming from the green transition. In fact, besides the risk of increasing regional polarization across EU regions, climate change also threatens socioeconomic cohesion within and across countries.

At a more granular level, Guzzardi et al. (2024) explore the repercussions of extreme events on income distribution in Italy at the municipality level. Results show that the most adverse consequences are borne by the lower income groups, while having no impact on the top income earners. Using higher-resolution topographic or spatial data, another strand of the literature has explored social vulnerability to specific climatic event in a particular area, for instance, heatwaves in Italy (D'Ambrosio, Di Martino, & Miraglia, 2023) or river-floods in Germany (Fekete, 2009).

While all the cited studies broaden our understanding of the economic and distributional effects of climate change, they do not fully pinpoint which sociodemographic characteristics make individuals especially vulnerable to climatic risks, offering limited guidance on who policies should prioritize and protect. This is particularly important given the European institutions' recognition of the need for a social just transition (European Commission, 2020), which emphasizes the crucial goal of leaving no one behind in the climate adaptation process. After assessing whether the European Green Deal is really leaving no-one behind, Markkanen and Anger-Kraavi (2019) claim that a genuine commitment to a just transition requires adequate funding and targeted measures that support the most vulnerable, considering the cumulative effects of multiple disadvantages.

2.2 Climate change: risk dimensions and unequal vulnerabilities

The impacts of climate change have far-reaching consequences in many domains, posing a range of interconnected risks (Palencia-Esteban and Valentini, 2025). While some of these risks stem directly from climatic phenomena, many are shaped or amplified by existing socio-economic conditions. In what follows, we outline three key climate-related risks—energy, transport and health—alongside a fourth, cross-cutting dimension: socio-economic vulnerability. Although not a climate risk per se, accounting for this interaction is essential to understanding the full scope and unequal distribution of climate risks.

Energy: Krstić et al. (2024) show that energy poverty is a reality for European households, especially in southern and eastern countries. Global warming is projected to bring a significant southwest-to-northeast decrease of heating-degree days and a smaller north-to-south increase of cooling-degree days (Coppola et al., 2021). Although heating demand is expected to decrease in winter and cooling demand to increase in summer, Wenz, et al. (2017) identify a north–south polarization of European electricity consumption under future warming. Besides the potential to widen existing regional gaps in energy consumption, poorer households are expected to face more difficulties coping with increasing energy prices.

Transport: The recent cost of living crisis has been mainly fueled by spiking energy prices, causing substantial social costs across the EU (Menyhért, 2022). On average, half of the total household energy bill is devoted to fuel or transport services in the EU (Alonso-Epelde, García-Muros and González-Eguino, 2024). In this context, transport poverty has become a salient concern, especially given its potential to disconnect individuals from essential services, such as health centers, or even the labour market. Furthermore, while policy efforts to 'green' the transport sector will require substantial decarbonization, extreme climate events such as heatwaves may lead individuals to increasingly rely on private transport. High temperatures can reduce the attractiveness and usability of public transport due to inadequate air conditioning, long waiting times at exposed stops or overcrowding. This shift could exacerbate inequalities, as those without access to private transport may face greater difficulties in maintaining mobility. The regional dimension also becomes relevant, as well-connected urban areas with proper public transport networks will be more resilient than the isolated rural areas.

Health: The more frequent and intense extreme weather events have already impacted on human health in Europe. Heat-related mortality and morbidity is expected to increase, especially in the South, with the elderly, children and those suffering from pre-existing medical conditions being particularly exposed (Bednar-Friedl et al., 2022). Air pollution is already a big public health concern, and poor air quality has the potential to exacerbate existing respiratory problems and cause new ones (Orru et al., 2017). Moreover, climate change strongly contributes to the spread of some allergenic plants, and allergies may become a more widespread health problem across Europe (EASAC, 2019), together with climate-sensitive infectious diseases, which may also expand as climatic conditions change. Despite all the potential adverse health impacts, it is crucial to identify those already suffering from cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, as they already are more vulnerable.

Socio-economic conditions: While not a direct consequence of climate change, socio-economic vulnerability plays a crucial role in shaping individuals' capacity to cope with and adapt to climate-related shocks (Hallegatte and Rozenberg, 2017). Limited financial resources, poor living conditions and weak labour market attachment can amplify the adverse effects of climate impacts, reducing resilience and increasing exposure to risks. Conversely, better socio-economic conditions can act as a protective factor, enabling households to access adaptive measures, such as improved housing, mobility or healthcare. Identifying vulnerable groups is therefore essential to prevent climate change from exacerbating existing inequalities.

3. Methodology

3.1 Identification: risk dimensions and vulnerabilities

This paper aims to explore which individuals are more exposed to climate-related risks in Europe. In the context of climate change impacts, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defines risk as resulting from the interaction of three elements: hazard, exposure, and vulnerability. Hazards are the potential occurrence of a natural event like floods or heatwaves. Exposure refers to who or what is in harm's way, such as people, infrastructure or ecosystems located in affected areas. Vulnerability is about the propensity or predisposition to be adversely affected, how badly they will be affected, and whether they can respond or adapt.

Based on the literature review and data availability, in this paper we consider four climate related risks affecting individuals (energy and food poverty and two health problems), each one being shaped by the interaction of these three components. Yet, in our framework we study the joint distribution of all four climate related risks together with three risk amplifying socioeconomic conditions, thus offering a multidimensional perspective. Departing from the IPCC's definition, we refer to cumulative exposure as the situation where individuals are simultaneously affected in the areas we are considering. We consider that such cumulative exposure makes individuals cumulatively vulnerable, so both concepts are interchangeably used in the text.

Our approach requires merging information from different data sources to capture the potential dimensions previously discussed. We take the 2019 EU Statistics on Income and Living Conditions (EU-SILC) cross-sectional data as the core data, as it provides a nationally representative sample and rich socioeconomic information. The variables capturing different climatic risks are in most cases estimates in other topic-specific data, i.e. auxiliary datasets, and matched into the core data. This matching exercise is explained below, after we discuss how we measure each dimension.

Energy and transport: We measure risk using energy and transport consumption data from the Household Budget Survey (HBS), as detailed in the data section. We rely on different indicators of energy/transport poverty or insecurity. For a comprehensive review on energy poverty indices, see Castaño-Rosa et al. (2019). Alonso-Epelde, García-Muros and González-Eguino (2024) recently expanded the analysis and metrics to transport poverty. Following their work, we apply the 10%, 2 times the median (2M) and low-income high-cost (LIHC) indicators to the following two expenditures: energy (electricity, gas and other fuels) and the combination of fuels for personal

transport equipment (diesel, petrol and other fuels) and medium-distance public transport (railway, bus, and combined transport). After equalizing expenditures and net income, which depends on the household they live, we identify energy and transport poor people:

- 10%: at risk if it spends more than 10% of its budget on energy/transport expenses.
- 2M: at risk if the share of total expenditure devoted to energy/transport is more than double the national median.
- LIHC: at risk if disposable income, after subtracting housing and energy/transport costs, falls below the poverty threshold (60% of the national median) and if expenditures on energy/transport are over the national median.

Health: We use the European Health Interview Survey (EHIS). We consider a person at risk if she experienced any of the following diseases and chronic conditions in the past 12 months: respiratory problems (having either asthma, bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease or emphysema) and cardiovascular problems (having either myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, angina pectoris, high blood pressure or a stroke).

Socio-economic conditions: We rely on EU-SILC. We consider three indicators, each capturing a distinct dimension of vulnerability: individuals at risk of poverty, those who are severely materially and socially deprived, and those living in households with very low work intensity. Overall, our definition captures individuals who, due to limited resources or challenging living conditions, are more likely to suffer the negative consequences of climate-related shocks and are less equipped to adapt.

3.2 Cross-survey matching

We use data from multiple sources (HBS, EHIS and EU-SILC, presented in Section 4) to measure individuals' exposure to risks across different regions. Unfortunately, these surveys capture only a single risk dimension, limiting our ability to analyse their interdependence, and lack sufficient socioeconomic data to fully understand the underlying determinants of these risks. To address this gap, we need to impute the estimated risks from these sources into a single dataset. We selected EU-SILC, as it offers a comprehensive view of the socioeconomic characteristics of individuals across European countries and regions. The imputation thus relies on the specific common variables shared between each origin data source (HBS and EHIS) and EU-SILC.

Risk projections are estimated and imputed into the EU-SILC data using socioeconomic and demographic variables that describe each individual. Since the available information differs across surveys, the imputation process accounts for these variations to ensure consistency. We use LASSO regressions, a well-known statistical learning method that selects the most relevant variables while preventing overfitting, thus maximizing the out of sample prediction. The model is optimized through a 5-fold cross-validation and applied separately to each country. For each country the shrinkage tuning parameter that maximizes the area under the ROC curve is selected (see Friedman et al. (2010) for the exact implementation of the algorithm).²

² We also tested whether using random forests would significantly improve prediction accuracy at a moderate additional computational cost. However, the results—based on a random subset of countries and domains—were clearly negative. The predictive performance of conditional inference random forests did not systematically outperform our baseline approach with substantial computational costs. Detailed results on predictive accuracy are available upon request.

In the end, the imputed risks are probabilities that depend on the set of common socioeconomic factors across datasets. To ensure that the predicted distribution of risk matches the original data, we impose an additional constraint: the proportion of affected individuals in each country must be the same as in the donor survey. This way, we ensure that the overall prevalence of risk remains unchanged while integrating the richer socioeconomic data available in EU-SILC.³ After performing the matching, each individual in EU-SILC is assigned with a predicted probability of being energy or transport poor, and suffering from cardiovascular or respiratory problems.

The cross-survey matching exercise allows us to perform two important analyses: first, to estimate, for each individual, a predicted risk in each domain, which we interpret as a measure of the extent to which the individual is exposed to the risk. This makes it possible to map the average risk in European regions, both by risk type and by summarizing them into a scalar representing the cumulative risk (e.g., average, minimum, maximum risk). Moreover, we can investigate the predictors of this risk in terms of socioeconomic characteristics, assessing the relative importance of different factors such as area of residence, gender, income, education, etc.

Note that the variables reflecting the socioeconomic conditions are available in EU-SILC, there is no need to perform a matching, but these are binary variables, the individual is either vulnerable or not. As our analysis relies on the probability of being at risk, we run three probit models, one for each of the socioeconomic conditions (poverty, deprivation and low work intensity), and estimate the predicted probability of being vulnerable.

3.3 Cumulative exposure: regional perspective

After constructing the key variables and performing the matching exercise, each individual in EU-SILC is assigned a probability of being exposed to energy-, health-, and socioeconomic-related risk factors. We draw on the inequality and concentration literature (Decancq 2014, Decancq 2020; García-Gómez, Pérez, and Prieto-Alaiz, 2021) to analyse the distribution of exposure from a multidimensional perspective. Using the probabilities of exposure across the seven dimensions under consideration, we derive three key indicators for each individual: the minimum, maximum, and the average risk. These values are aggregated at the NUTS regional level to provide a comprehensive overview of risk distribution across Europe. Additionally, we identify the most relevant risk factor in each region.

To assess inequality in risk distribution within regions, we estimate the Gini index for the distribution of average risks. High Gini coefficients indicate that the exposure is concentrated within a subset of the population, whereas lower values suggest a more homogeneous distribution -where most individuals are either highly vulnerable, unaffected, or moderately exposed.

Although the average risk captures an overall effect, the scope of this analysis is limited. First, the same average risk can represent different exposure patterns: one individual may face moderate risk across all dimensions, while another may be highly vulnerable in one area, such as health, but unaffected in others. By definition, the average risk masks information about risk composition, which is essential for understanding dependencies. Second, one could consider two societies: in the first, individuals experience medium exposure levels across all risks, while in the second, individuals are

³ A systematic misalignment of predicted probabilities with average risk in the donor survey can depend on a different distribution of the characteristics used to perform cross-survey imputation.

highly vulnerable in some dimensions but unaffected in others. Despite these differences, the Gini coefficient over the average risk may be very similar in both cases. Again, composition matters. When risks are highly dependent of each other, exposure in one area strongly predicts exposure in others. In such societies, knowing that an individual is at high risk in one dimension implies that they are likely at risk in multiple areas. Conversely, in a society with low dependence, individuals may be exposed to certain risks while remaining unaffected by others.

With these ideas in mind, we complement the analysis of the Gini on the averaged risk with the degree of dependence in risk exposure at the regional level, thus providing a broader perspective by examining the composition of risk distribution. Our dependence analysis follows Decancq (2020), whose approach resembles the Gini index in inequality measurement. However, rather than focusing on cumulative deprivation and affluence, we introduce the concepts of cumulative vulnerabilities and immunity. In this setting, cumulative vulnerabilities arise when individuals are highly exposed to all considered dimensions simultaneously, while cumulative immunity occurs when certain individuals face little or no risks. Dependence captures both phenomena, effectively highlighting the extremes of the distribution, those who are most and least exposed.

To quantify dependence, we use the diagonal dependence diagram and metrics proposed by Decancq (2020). The diagram consists of two curves: the downward (D_x) and upward (\bar{D}_x) diagonal dependence curves, derived from the diagonal sections of the underlying copula and survival functions, respectively (see Figure 1).

This method follows a position-based approach, where each individual is assigned a rank in each dimension based on their probability of being at risk. Individuals with higher probabilities occupy higher ranks. These ranks are expressed as percentile values, ranging from 0 to 100, indicating the proportion of the population with a lower position than the individual under consideration.⁴

From the positional vector, we derive each individual's maximum and minimum position, key to our analysis. Individuals with a high minimum position rank highly in all dimensions, indicating a high probability of being affected across all risk factors, i.e., they experience cumulative exposure. The higher the minimum position, the more severe the cumulative vulnerability. Conversely, individuals with a low maximum position would rank low in all dimensions, experiencing cumulative immunity, and facing little to no risk across all factors.

⁴ We might fall into the problem of ties, this is, how to assign the rank when two or more individuals obtain the same values. For a discussion, see Decancq (2014) and García-Gómez, Pérez and Prieto-Alaiz (2021). In case of a tie, we will rank individuals randomly, but we run 100 bootstrap repetitions to check the robustness and construct confidence intervals around our estimates.

Figure 1. Diagonal dependence diagram

Source: Decancq (2020).

These two concepts are linked to the diagram (Figure 1). The downward diagonal dependence index shows the population share that has a lower position in all dimensions, this is, the share that is less vulnerable with respect to that position. The upward curve shows the population share with a higher position in all dimensions, namely those who are more vulnerable. Overall, the larger the proportion of individuals who either outrank or are outranked by others, the stronger dependence is.

Both cumulative notions measure a different type of dependence (vulnerability and immunity), hence their combination provides a more complete picture. The diagonal dependence index is indeed based on the area below both curves in the diagonal dependence diagram - the shaded area of Figure 1. Formally, the area below curve D_x and \bar{D}_x is defined as:

$$\delta_m^-(X) = \frac{2(m+1) \int D_x(p) dp - 2}{m-1} \quad (1)$$

$$\delta_m^+(X) = \frac{2(m+1) \int \bar{D}_x dp - 2}{m-1} \quad (2)$$

where m the number of dimensions, 4 in our case. So, the diagonal dependence index equals:

$$DDI = \frac{\delta_m^-(X) + \delta_m^+(X)}{2} * 100 \quad (3)$$

This index equals 0 when there is no dependence between the dimensions and equals 100 when there is maximal dependence. We evaluate dependence at the regional level. The exposition of inequality (based on the Gini coefficients) and dependence levels captures different yet complementary aspects of risk exposure, as will be discussed in the results section.

3.4 Cumulative exposure: individual perspective

The previous analysis does not inform about the role played by sociodemographic characteristics. We explore the relative importance of sociodemographic factors in explaining the variability of the main dependent variable (the average risk for each individual within each country) using the conditional variable importance method for random forests proposed by Strobl et al. (2008). The underlying idea is simple: the conditional inference random forests introduced by Hothorn et al. (2006) predict the variability of a dependent variable by averaging the structures of multiple “trees” that partition the regressor space. Strobl et al. (2008) propose generating a single tree, that partitions the regressors space after permuting the values of a predictor variable X_j thus eliminating its original association with the dependent variable. The importance of X_j is measured by assessing the decline in prediction accuracy in the new tree compared to the original model without permutation. The intuition is that if X_j is important for predicting the dependent variable, the prediction accuracy should decrease substantially after the permutation of its values. Opposed, if X_j is not important, the accuracy in the prediction of the variability should remain largely unchanged.

Following this approach, we run 200 different trees for each country, each grown after permuting a random set of regressors, and then compute the average decline in prediction accuracy associated with each regressor. All parameters in random forest and variable importance settings are those found as default in Hothorn et al. (2015). The regressors used to explain the variability in the dependent variable, the average risk exposure, include educational level, sex, country of birth, age, household size, housing tenure, household income, and the sector and occupation (both at 1 digit). To simplify the exposition of results we cluster all regions by country, and thus introduce the region of residence as a potential factor to explain disparities in risk. Finally, we normalize the results, so that the sum of all relative importance scores within each country equals 100%. Besides highlighting the factors that contribute most to geographic disparities, we also pinpoint some of the most vulnerable populations.

We also identify some of the most vulnerable subgroups in Europe. The analysis follows a similar approach: for each country, we run a conditional regression tree to explain the experienced risk as a function of the same set of regressors (see Hothorn et al. (2006) for details). The algorithm partitions the regressor space into non-overlapping regions, allowing us to identify particularly vulnerable groups. To address the typical problem of high sampling variance associated with interpreting a single tree, we adopt a conservative approach: a split is allowed only when the p-value of the correlation test used to justify the split is below 0.0001. This means we are commenting on groups identified by a tree estimated with 99.99% confidence—well above the standard threshold in statistical analysis. Moreover, we impose a minimum number of observations to identify a group equal to 1% of the sample. These precautions are necessary to avoid the risk of identifying misleading groups.

3.5 Future projections

To understand which sociodemographic groups will be mostly affected by climate change, we consider future climate scenarios and project exposure under alternative futures. As in Campagnolo et al. (2023), we first study the historical correlation between climate-related hazards and the variables capturing climate related risks at the individual level. Combining the estimated historical statistical relationships with future climate scenarios we then derive projections of climate change exposure for the European population. We take two steps.

First, we determine the statistical relationship between climate-related hazards and potential climate related risks. This exercise requires both historical climate and socioeconomic data, all data detail are in Section 4. Formally, for each individual i in year t and region r , we run the next regression.

$$y_{itr} = \alpha + \sum_j \beta_j C_{jitr} + \theta X_{itr} + \mu_t + \mu_r + \varepsilon_{itr} \quad (4)$$

All dependent variables y_{itr} (dichotomous variables indicating whether a person is at risk in the energy, transport and health dimensions) are modelled as functions of climate variables C_{jitr} . We consider different climatic variables (j) for each dimension, including yearly average surface air temperature (tas), annual total precipitation (pr), and other variables defined in Section 4.2. Linear and non/linear climatic relationships are considered, thus C_{jitr} enters as a quadratic polynomial. All specifications control for personal sociodemographic characteristics, which vary depending on the dimension being explored and data availability (all tables describe the included controls). We additionally control for country fixed effects (μ_r), accounting for all time-invariant socioeconomic and geographical factors, while year-specific macroeconomic shocks are captured by year fixed effects (μ_t). Errors are clustered at the regional level.

In a second step, the estimated coefficients ($\hat{\beta}_j$) together with future climate and socio-economic scenarios are used to define the future pathways of risk for Europe around 2050. Modeled climate projections are derived from the multi-model collection of CMIP6 (the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, Phase 6; Eyring, 2016). CMIP offers a standardized experimental framework for studying climate change.⁵ Out of the possible pathways, we consider a moderate (SSP2-RCP4.5) and severe (SSP5-RCP8.5) climate change scenarios. SSP2-4.5 depicts a "middle of the road" scenario where emissions remain steady near current levels before gradually declining around mid-century, with net-zero only achieved after 2100. In contrast, SSP5-8.5 envisions a future characterized by intensified fossil fuel use and highly integrated global markets, it represents a worse-case scenario.

As explained in Appendix A2, future projections of selected climate and hazard metrics are obtained by calculating the difference between CMIP6 model outputs for the mid-century period (2040–2059) and the simulated historical baseline (1995–2014) and adding it to the historical climate data.

The risks related to socioeconomic conditions are not directly linked to climate change; rather, we consider them as second-order factors that have the potential to attenuate or amplify the effects of climate shocks. Accordingly, the projections of these risks are not climate-dependent but

⁵ Specifically, a set of scenarios were chosen to provide a range of distinct end-of-century climate change outcomes by combining the Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs) and Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs). The SSP-RCP scenarios are widely used global climate frameworks that merge baseline socio-economic narratives (SSPs) with various emissions trajectories derived from the RCPs (O'Neill et al., 2016).

population-dependent. We use age- and sex-specific population projections for 2050 to adjust individual survey weights. This reweighting ensures that the age-sex structure of the data aligns with the projected regional populations provided by Eurostat (EUROPOP2019). The resulting dataset enables forward-looking analyses of socioeconomic conditions under future demographic scenarios.

4. Data

4.1 Socioeconomic datasets

Household Budget Surveys (HBS)

The European HBS collects detailed information on household expenditures, income sources and sociodemographic characteristics. Microdata is available for reference years 2010, 2015, and 2020. We use all three waves to conduct the historical climate analysis, while the most recent wave is employed for the matching exercise. The dataset provides granular insights into household consumption patterns. For this study, we focus on expenditures related to energy and transport. Table 1 presents the key variables used in the analysis. Regional data are disclosed at the NUTS 1 level, representing major socio-economic regions within the EU, so the historical analysis and projections are defined at this level.

Table 1. List of key variables in HBS

Variable	Code
Net household income	EUR_HH099
Total expenditure	EUR_HE00
OECD modified equivalence scale	HB062
Energy	EUR_HE045
Private transport (diesel, petrol, fuels for transport)	Germany: EUR_HE0722
	Others: EUR_HE07221 + EUR_HE07222 + EUR_HE07223
Public transport (railway, road/bus, combined transport)	Germany: EUR_HE0731+ EUR_HE0732 +
	Others: EUR_HE0731 + EUR_HE07321 + EUR_HE0735

Source: Household Budget Surveys.

European health interview survey (EHIS)

The EHIS comprises four modules addressing health status, healthcare use, health determinants, and socio-economic background characteristics. The survey targets individuals aged 15 and older residing in private households. Data is available from three waves: the first conducted between 2006 and 2009, the second between 2013 and 2015, and the third in 2019. All three waves are used for historical analysis, with the third wave being selected for the matching. The dataset covers all EU27 countries, but regional information is only available in the third wave for 20 countries. Consequently, the relationship between climate-related hazards and health outcomes is analyzed at the country level.⁶

To assess potential climate-related health outcomes, we focus on variables indicating whether an individual has respiratory conditions (asthma, bronchitis, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, emphysema) or cardiovascular issues (myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, angina pectoris, high blood pressure, or stroke). The following questions are used to identify those health problems:

i) *Do you or have you ever had any of the following diseases/conditions?*, ii) *Was this disease/condition diagnosed by a medical doctor?*, iii) *Have you had this disease/condition in the past 12 months?*, and iv) *Have you taken any medicine for this disease/condition in the last two weeks?*

EU statistics on income and living conditions (EU-SILC)

We take the 2019 EU-SILC cross sectional data as the core data, as it provides an up-to-date nationally representative sample and rich socioeconomic information, allowing for a richer match with the other datasets. The data is available for all EU27 countries, the regions being reported at NUTS 1 level. EU-SILC also provides information to measure socioeconomic vulnerability, which may amplify the adverse effects of climate change. We consider the indicators used by Eurostat to measure At-risk-of-poverty or social exclusion rate (AROPE).⁷

- At risk of poverty: individuals with an equivalized disposable income (after social transfer) below 60 % of the national median.
- Severe material and social deprivation: it measures an enforced lack of necessary and desirable items to lead an adequate life. The indicator considers the affordability of certain goods, services or social activities. It identifies the population experiencing an enforced lack of at least 7 out of 13 deprivation items (6 related to the individual and 7 related to the household).
- Living in households with low work intensity: those individuals whose household members of working age worked a working time equal or less than 20% of their total work-time potential during the previous year.

⁶ An alternative data source is SHARE (Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe), which collects health outcomes and provides regional information at the NUTS 1 level. It is yet limited to individuals aged 50 and older, resulting in a more restrictive sample selection. We have verified that the distribution of cardiovascular and respiratory conditions is homogeneous across regions, which mitigates concerns about conducting the historical analysis at the country level.

⁷ Further details are provided by Eurostat: [https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:At_risk_of_poverty_or_social_exclusion_\(AROPE\)](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:At_risk_of_poverty_or_social_exclusion_(AROPE))

4.2 Climate data

Historical and projected unweighted climate variables are obtained from the World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal (CCKP). For the historical climate, we take the ERA5 reanalysis data, which is the fifth generation ECMWF atmospheric reanalysis of the global climate covering the period from January 1940 to present. We retrieve the following list of climate indicators at the grid cell level for the period 2011–2022, corresponding with the available survey years:

- Mean temperature (TAS). Average near-surface air temperature over the year (in °C).
- Cooling degree days (CDD) and Heating degree days (HDD). The cumulative number of degrees that the daily average temperature is above (below) a specified threshold (here 65°F or 18°C) in a year, which is a measurement designed to quantify the demand for energy needed to cool (warm) a building, respectively.
- Number of hot days (HD30), very hot days (HD35). The number of days with daily maximum temperature being equal or over 30 and 35°C, respectively, during a year.
- Number of frost days (FD). The average aggregated number of days where the daily minimum temperature is below 0°C in a year.
- Precipitations (PR). Aggregated accumulated precipitation in a year (in mm).
- Number of heavy (r20mm) precipitation days. The number of days with precipitation over 20mm during the year.

We aggregate gridded data at the regional and country level. In particular, NUTS 1 and 2, as these are the administrative boundaries provided in our socioeconomic data. However, simply aggregating climate data without considering the geography of socio-economic activities may bias climate impact assessments, particularly when regional variability is key to identifying effects (Hsiang, 2013, Gortan et al., 2024). Thus, we follow the literature and derive population-weighted climate indicators. We resort to the historical gridded population dataset from the GHS-POP gridded population, provided by the European Commission. It depicts residential population estimates between 1975 and 2020 in 5-year intervals. We apply linear projections to get yearly population estimates, calculating the arithmetic population growth rates and performing interpolations.⁸ Finally, we compute the population weighted regional climate indicators for years 2011–2022.⁹

For the future projections, we use projected climate variables from 30 CMIP6 climate models provided by the CCKP.¹⁰ As outlined in Appendix A2, future climate is also aggregated by NUTS regions using population weights. In the case of future, we use SSP-consistent population projections (Jones and O'Neill, 2016) and the Gridded Population of the World (GPWv4) collection, both available at the CCKP.

⁸ Alternatively, we could modify the concurrent weighting strategy in Gortan et al. (2024), weighting climate variables using the population count closest in time. For example, climate metrics for 2010–2014 (inclusive) are weighted using population data from 2010.

⁹ Note that NUTS legislation is amended periodically, so different NUTS classifications are used in different waves of the employed surveys. We estimate all regional climate variables using NUTS 2016 classification and apply the NUTS converter (Joint Research Centre, 2022) to derive versions.

¹⁰ World Bank (2024) lists the models. We use ensemble values from each of the models in the collection and take the median across the individual model. This leads to more robust projections than those produced by any individual model.

5. Results

5.1 Exposure at present: energy, transport and socioeconomic conditions

We begin the exposition of results by presenting some descriptive statistics of the dimensions under examination, using the original “auxiliary” datasets and focusing on the share of the population exposed to each channel. Table 2 provides insights into the prevalence of energy and transport poverty at the European level across time. Table B1 in the Appendix provides additional descriptives to better understand country-based patterns. Over the period under consideration, at the EU level, there is a consistent decline according to the 10% indicator, while the two times the median (2M) and the low-income high-cost (LIHC) indicators remain stable.

Across-category comparisons reveal differences in both the extent and persistence of energy poverty. Among the energy indicators, the LIHC index appears to be the most persistent, suggesting that energy insecurity is driven not only by high energy costs but also by structural income constraints. In fact, Table B1 reveals that energy poverty is lowest in Northern and Central European countries: 7% of the population is vulnerable in Finland and Sweden, and 11% in the Netherlands. In contrast, energy poverty is more pronounced in South-Eastern countries, where 15% or more of the population is considered poor.

However, the 2M indicator offers a contrasting picture. According to this measure, Denmark, Finland, and Sweden have the highest share of energy-poor. This is due to the relatively low share of income spent on energy in these countries, which results in a low national median. Since the 2M threshold is based on this median, more people surpass it and are thus classified as energy poor. As discussed in Alonso-Epelde (2023), both the 10% and 2M indicators are more prone to false positives.

In contrast, the LIHC indicator yields the smallest share of transport poor. There is still geographical heterogeneity, Southern countries and the Czech Republic face the highest values (see Table B3). Surprisingly, transport poverty appears as a residual issue in Eastern Europe, with only 2% to 4% of the population identified as vulnerable in countries such as Bulgaria, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania and Romania. A closer look reveals that many low-income households in Eastern Europe do not spend money on transport at all. Among those who do, expenditures are often minimal and fall below the national median threshold, meaning they are not captured as poor under the LIHC measure. Ultimately, the LIHC indicator fails to identify hidden transport poverty—cases in which individuals cannot afford even the minimum necessary level of transport. The 2M indicator identifies more at-risk individuals in the East, but the levels are still relatively low.

Table 2. Energy and transport vulnerability over time.

Year	2010	2015	2020
Energy 10	15.08	13.32	9.29
Energy 2m	13.60	12.53	11.74
Energy LIHC	14.81	14.92	14.56
Transport 10	12.45	10.82	7.74
Transport 2m	11.81	11.89	11.47
Transport LIHC	8.06	8.09	7.91

Source: Household Budget Surveys

Table 3. Share of people with respiratory and cardiovascular issues over time.

Index	2006-09	2013-15	2019
Cardiovascular	21,95	22,77	24,55
Respiratory	9,07	8,69	8,02

Source: European health interview survey.

Regarding the health dimension, Table 3 illustrates that the prevalence of cardiovascular conditions has steadily increased, rising from 22% in 2006–09 to 24% in 2019. In contrast, respiratory issues have remained constant, at around 8-9%. Looking at the country profiles presented in Table B2, although cardiovascular problems are more prevalent than the respiratory ones everywhere, the former is particularly salient in Hungary, Latvia or Lithuania, whereas the latter is more salient in France, Finland or Iceland.

Moving to those factor that might amplify climate related vulnerabilities, Appendix Table B3 presents the share of individuals who are at risk of poverty, who suffer from severe material and social deprivation, and who live in a household with low work intensity in each country. Countries such as Bulgaria, Romania and Latvia report the highest combined levels, with over 20% of the population at risk of poverty and high deprivation levels. In contrast, Austria, Finland and the Netherlands show lower vulnerability, particularly in terms of deprivation. Notably, Greece stands out with simultaneously high levels of work intensity and deprivation, highlighting more multidimensional vulnerability. Overall, poverty emerges as the most salient risk among the three indicators, being more prominent in the South and East Europe. The other dimensions are also visible in these regions, with low work intensity especially pronounced in the Mediterranean area, and deprivation more concentrated in the East.

5.2 Climate change in Europe

This section examines the geographical distribution of key climate variables across Europe (presented in Section 4.2). We set the historical period 1995–2014 as the reference point, providing a climatological baseline at the NUTS2 regional level. We also assess projected changes by 2050, focusing on climate anomalies under two future scenarios: SSP2-4.5 (moderate emissions) and SSP5-8.5 (high-emissions, severe warming). Given the technical details discussed in Appendix A, the anomaly is expressed in relative changes for precipitation. Regardless of the employed measure, all projections offer insights into potential climate shifts and their regional variations across Europe.

Figure 2 shows that the historical temperature distribution (TAS) across Europe follows a clear north-south gradient, with warmer conditions in Southern Europe and colder climates in the north. Projected temperature anomalies indicate a significant warming trend, particularly in Northern and Eastern Europe, where temperature increases exceed 2°C under SSP2-4.5 and 2.5°C under SSP5-8.5. The figure also highlights the dry and wet regions. As projections suggest, reduced rainfall is expected in the Mediterranean and a moderate increase in Scandinavian countries under both scenarios. Yet, a drier climate is anticipated across much of Europe under SSP5-8.5.

This geographical pattern consistently appears when looking at other climatic variables. Figure 3 illustrates the spatial distribution of hot days (HD30: mean temperature above 30°C) and frost days (FD: minimum temperature below 0°C). The historical baseline (1995–2014) again depicts a clear north-south division, with higher Hd30 values in southern regions and more frost days in northern and continental areas. Yet, future projections under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 indicate a significant increase in HD30, particularly in southern Europe, while frost days are expected to decline, especially in northern and central regions.

These shifts highlight the intensification of heat extremes and the reduction of cold extremes, with potential implications for ecosystems, infrastructure, and human health. In fact, as noted in Masson-Delmotte et al. (2021), the most significant warming is anticipated in northeastern Europe, northern Scandinavia, and inland regions of Mediterranean countries. In contrast, the least warming is expected in western Europe, particularly in the United Kingdom, Ireland, western France, the Benelux countries, and Denmark.

Figure 2. Historic climate and projection: average temperature and precipitation.

Temp 1995-2014

Temp. Anomaly 2-4.5

Temp. Anomaly 5-8.5

Pr 1995-2014

Pr. Delta 2-4.5

Pr. Delta 5-8.5

Source: World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & CCKP.

Figure 3. Historic climate and projection: hot days and frost days.

Source: World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & CCKP.

Figure 4. Historic climate and projection: cooling degree days and heating degree days.

Source: World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & CCKP.

This storyline also applies to cooling and heating degree days, designed to describe the energy requirements of buildings in terms of heating (HDD) or cooling (CDD). Looking at Figure 4, higher CDD values are found in southern regions, particularly in Spain, Italy, and Greece, where cooling demand is more pronounced. Conversely, the HDD distribution follows an inverse pattern, with higher values historically observed in northern Europe, where heating demand is greater. While future projections indicate a significant increase in CDD across Europe, especially in southern and central regions, we also identify a substantial decrease in HDD, particularly in northern and central regions, as winters become milder. This pattern holds under both scenarios, but note that the HDD reduction/CDD increase is more pronounced under SSP5-8.5. Overall, the figure highlights the changing energy demands driven by climate change, with increasing cooling needs and decreasing heating requirements. Complementing the overall picture, Figure B1 provides the distribution of very hot days (hd5) and heavy precipitation (r20mm) days.

5.3 Historical relation between climate hazards and climate-related risks

While the previous section provided descriptive statistics for all potential indicators that could be used to assess the energy and transport dimensions, the following sections will focus on a single key measure for each dimension. The other definition will serve as robustness. We have selected the indicators according to two criteria. First, we have theoretical or conceptual considerations. The 10% and 2M indicators often lead to more false positives, but the LIHC indicator can fail to identify hidden poverty. In the case of energy poverty, the 10% indicator suggests that over 20% of the population is vulnerable in most Eastern countries, while the Nordic countries become the most exposed under the 2M index. Given the risk of false positives, the LIHC becomes the most reliable option, as it also provides a spatial pattern found in other studies. Measuring transport poverty with LIHC, we identify few vulnerable individuals in Eastern Europe, making hidden poverty a concern. In this case, the 2M or 10% indicators fit better in this case.

Second, the technical criteria. The number of affected individuals for certain indicators is so low that applying machine learning algorithms to identify these individuals becomes highly unreliable. Concentrating on the most representative indicators ensures that the analysis remains both robust and meaningful, while avoiding the pitfalls of sparse data that could undermine the accuracy of machine learning models. This also explains why we excluded a dimension that we initially wanted to consider, “food insecurity”, from the list of modelled risks. Food insecurity is in fact virtually absent in several countries.

We need to choose the indicators that provide a better match in the “core” EU-SILC dataset. We use the (out of sample) area below the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) as a measure of the quality of the prediction model. The LIHC indicator provide the highest area, this is, they predict better with the data available, while the 10% underperform. Taking both criteria into account, we select energy LIHC and transport 2M.¹¹

To assess the link between climate and our risk indicators, we have estimated the regressions presented in Section 3.3. Table B4 in Appendix B presents the average marginal effects (AMEs) obtained from our probit regressions, where different climatic variables are used to predict the likelihood of an individual being energy (column 1) or transport poor (column 2) and having

¹¹ The LIHC indicators are not available for the Czech Republic and Italy, we match the 2M indicators for these countries.

respiratory (column 3) or cardiovascular (column 4) problems, as indicated by the different indicators. Table B5 provides the results for energy and transport using the other indicators as robustness.

The average marginal effects (AMEs) summarizes the overall effect in the sample by representing the average change in the predicted probability of being vulnerable to climate change when the given climate variable increases by one unit. Yet, average predicted value graphs allow us to visualize the full, potentially nonlinear relationship between the climatic variable and the predicted probabilities. We will mainly focus on the latter to extract as much information as possible and complement the analysis with the AMEs. Results should be interpreted with caution given the limited geospatial granularity level of our datasets, with poses challenges for the identification.

Starting with energy, the main climatic variables considered include cooling and heating degree days, as they proxy energy demand, and precipitation. The red line in Figure 5 represents the average predicted probability of experiencing energy poverty as a function of CDD, while the shaded blue area denotes the confidence interval around these predictions. The relationship follows an inverted U-shape. Initially, as CDD increases from low levels, the probability of energy poverty rises. This positive relationship suggests that moderate increases in cooling needs are associated with greater energy insecurity, likely due to the increased energy consumption required for cooling, which can strain household budgets. However, beyond a critical threshold -approximately 1,500 CDD - the probability of energy poverty begins to decline, indicating that adaptation strategies or infrastructure improvements may help offsetting this risk.

Figure 5. Average predicted probabilities energy: cooling-heating degree days and precipitation.

Source: World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & HBS.

It is important to keep in mind when interpreting Figure 5 and the other predicted probability plots that the distribution of the independent variable is highly uneven across the plotted range. For cooling degree days, as visible in the first panel of Figure 5, almost no region, except Cyprus, Greece and few regions in Spain have experienced a value above 1500. As a result, the estimated relationship appears positive and concave across all European regions except few exceptions.

Table B4 reveals a small but statistically significant positive AMEs for both CDD and HDD, suggesting a positive average effect. Figure 5 shows a clear upward trend for HDD, indicating that the probability of energy poverty increases with cold weather, which boosts energy demand. Finally, Figure 5 also unmasks a negative relationship between precipitation and energy poverty, also captured in the AME. Very low levels of precipitation are particularly associated with higher energy vulnerability rates. Indeed, arid climates (low precipitation) often experience extreme temperature fluctuations, raising heating and cooling demands.

In the case of transport, we have considered both temperature and precipitation (Figure 6). For temperature, we identify a U-shaped curve, indicating that lower and higher temperatures are associated with more transport poverty. In extreme heat or cold, active transport modes such as walking and cycling become less viable, forcing greater dependence on motorized transport, increasing household transport expense. In contrast, the negative relationship observed for precipitation suggests that higher levels of rainfall may reduce the probability of transport poverty, potentially by discouraging travel or altering mobility patterns. The AMEs provide a similar picture, also with the LIHC and 10% indicators (see Table B4 and B5).

Figure 6. Average predicted probabilities transport: temperature and precipitation.

Source: World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & HBS.

Exploring the health outcomes, Figures 7 and 8 show the average predicted probabilities (response functions) of respiratory and cardiovascular problems in relation to selected climatic variables. For respiratory issues, the left panel shows a clear negative relationship, with more frost days associated with a lower likelihood of reporting respiratory problems. For cardiovascular problems, we observe a U-shaped relationship with very hot days. The probability of cardiovascular problems initially falls, but rises again beyond a certain threshold, likely capturing the adverse health effects of repeated heat stress at extreme temperatures.

These results, also reflected in the AMEs, seem contra intuitive and are likely linked to the level of granularity of the data. The EHIS does not offer regional-level data, so our historical climate analysis relies on country-level climate data. This limitation may underestimate regional disparities in climate-induced health risks and influence the estimated relationship. Nevertheless, we have checked that fitted values, which predict health risks for specific climatic conditions, provide coherent relations. Unlike average predicted probabilities, which summarise the effect across the entire sample, fitted values reflect the probability health problems in the observed climatic and socio-economic context of each individual. As shown in Appendix Figure B3, more frost days (very hot days) are positively correlated with a higher probability of respiratory (cardiovascular) health issues. This results ultimately reflects country patterns: in colder/warmer regions there are more respiratory/cardiovascular problems.

Lastly, heavy precipitation days exhibit a non-linear and positive relationship with health outcomes. The probability of both respiratory and cardiovascular problems increases with more frequent heavy rain events but tends to decline at very high levels of rainfall. This pattern may reflect short-term adverse health impacts associated with extreme precipitation, while very frequent heavy rain may lead to behavioral adaptation or reduced outdoor exposure, mitigating health risks.

Figure 7. Average predicted probabilities respiratory problems: frost and heavy rain days.

Source: World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & EHIS.

Figure 8. Average predicted probabilities cardiovascular problem: very hot and heavy rain days.

Source: **Source:** World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & EHIS.

5.4 Cumulative exposure: regional analysis

This section analyzes the geographical distribution of cumulative exposure across Europe by examining average risks at regional level and discussing the most salient risk factors in each area. We then assess the (in)equality in the risk distribution within regions using the Gini coefficient and the diagonal dependence index. Finally, we investigate which socioeconomic factors and individual characteristics determine average risk at the individual level.

In our framework, risk is assessed across seven dimensions: 4 climate related risks (energy and transport poverty, and cardiovascular and respiratory problems) and three amplifying factors (poverty, deprivation and low work intensity). After performing the matching exercise discussed in Section 3.2, everyone has a probability of being affected by these risk factors, from which three key indicators are derived: the average probability of experiencing risk across all dimensions, and the highest and lowest probability of risk in any dimension, which capture the minimal and maximal risk faced by the person. These values are then aggregated at the NUTS regional level to provide a comprehensive overview of risk distribution across Europe.

Figure 9 presents the distribution of average risk across European regions. The mean probability of experiencing risk is around 0.12, but there are notable regional disparities. Exposure is higher in the Mediterranean, especially in southern areas, and Eastern Europe, namely in Bulgaria. In contrast, some Flemish region, French areas, Navarre (north Spain) the North-West Romania outstand for its lower risk levels, suggesting a lower exposure. While the average risk can provide an overall picture, it does not capture the full extent of the phenomena. We thus complement the analysis by looking at the lowest and highest risks.

Figure 9. Average risk by region.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Examining the lowest risk (Appendix, Figure B3), we observe that a substantial proportion of the population is not exposed in at least one dimension. Note that the indicator persons living in households with very low work intensity excludes households composed only of children, of students aged less than 25 and/or people aged 65 or more. Some people are thus risk-free, contributing to small values of lowest risk. Even if the map highlights Southern and Eastern Europe and parts of France as slightly riskier, these values remain rather small. Conversely, the highest risk (Appendix, Figure B4) shows significant variation across regions. In some areas, individuals experience extremely high exposure in at least one dimension, with values reaching approximately 0.45. The most affected regions belong to the Mediterranean countries, the Baltic states and other Eastern areas, especially Bulgaria.

While the spatial distribution of total risk is informative, it does not specify which risk factor is the most relevant one in each area. Figure 10 presents the average risk probability by dimension across countries (Appendix Figure B5 shows results by region). Several key trends emerge.

Cardiovascular risks present the highest probability across most countries, indicating a widespread health related vulnerability. The highest exposure is found in Germany, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Hungary, Poland, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland and Portugal, where cardiovascular issues dominate individual risk profiles. This Eastern pattern is also found when looking at regional data on rates of deaths from coronary heart diseases provided by Eurostat.¹²

Poverty—defined as having an equivalised disposable income below 60% of the national median—is also a prominent risk, particularly in southern and eastern countries such as Greece, Italy, Spain, Latvia, Bulgaria and Romania. This indicator measures low income in comparison to other residents in that country, which ultimately points to more unequal income distribution.

¹² Eurostat. Causes of death - standardised death rate by NUTS 2 region of residence: https://doi.org/10.2908/HLTH_CD_ASDR2

Figure 10. Average risk by dimension and country.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Two additional climate-related risks are also noteworthy. While energy poverty affects many countries, it is particularly significant in Southern and Eastern European nations, where energy insecurity remains a major concern, as highlighted by Krstić et al. (2024). Transport poverty is more homogeneously distributed across Europe, with no clear geographical patterns.

Respiratory issues, low work intensity and severe material and social deprivation are, on average, secondary concerns. However, notable geographical divides exist. Respiratory problems are more prevalent in Central and Northern Europe, while risks related to deprivation and low work intensity are concentrated in Southern Europe, with Bulgaria and Greece also standing out in terms of deprivation.

It is worth noting that the prevalence of non-climatic risks across Europe contributes to the spatial distribution observed in Figure 9. As summarized in Appendix Table B3, poverty and deprivation levels are significantly higher in Southern and Eastern Europe, while low work intensity is a greater concern in Mediterranean countries. Appendix Figure B6 illustrates the distribution of average risks when only the four climate-related variables are considered. In this case, higher risk levels are observed in Central and Eastern regions such as Hungary, Germany or the Czech Republic, highlighting their exposure to climate change. However, it is important to consider both dimensions,

climatic and AROPE-related vulnerability, together to gain a more holistic understanding of overall risk. Socioeconomic conditions can, in fact, either amplify or mitigate the negative effects of climate-related risks.

Moving to the distributional analysis, Figures 11 and 12 respectively present the degree of diagonal dependence across risk dimensions, and the Gini coefficient in the average risk exhibited by individuals in the population. Both sets of results are shown and commented on together because they attend to different but complementary dimensions of risk exposure. On the one hand, as explained in Section 3.4, dependence highlights how individuals are affected -or not- by several risks at the same time, emphasizing the cumulative dimension of exposure. On the other hand, the Gini coefficient reflects to what extent the average risk in a country or region is (un)equally distributed across its citizens. Different combinations of both indicators may lead to a more or less desirable situation, that may facilitate or harden policy interventions.

Figure 11. Diagonal Dependence across European Regions

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

The first group of countries we bundled are characterized by a low Gini coefficient combined with low dependence values. In particular, it seems that in Italy, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland and Latvia, the average exposure is more evenly distributed across individuals. The Gini coefficient is particularly low in the Czech Republic (around 0.21-0.24 Gini points, depending on the region) and Italy (around 0.27 across all regions), with dependence values being also minimal in the Czech Republic (up to 0.05), Hungary (around 0.07) and Italy (values equaling 0.08). This can be interpreted as risks in different dimensions -such as health, energy poverty and poverty- being largely independent from each other. As a consequence, individuals facing high risks in one area may remain unaffected by others, hence achieving a more balanced overall exposure across the population.

Figure 12. Gini in the average risk across European Regions

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

In the other extreme, both the Gini coefficient and dependence values are rather high in Cyprus, Ireland, Belgium, Austria, and to a lesser extent the Netherlands, where risk distribution is very unequal, with Gini values reaching or even surpassing 0.4 Gini points, like Cyprus (CY0) where Gini has 0.43 points. This implies that individuals are either heavily exposed to multiple risks at once, or largely unaffected. While this polarization may allow policymakers to more easily identify and target the most vulnerable populations, it also signals high levels of concentrated risk among certain population groups, making them particularly vulnerable.

Another distinct case is observed in Romania, Denmark, Greece and Sweden, where the Gini coefficient is relatively high, in most cases close or above 0.35 points, but dependence across

dimensions is relatively low, at least below the average, with values close to 0.10 in Denmark or Romania. This means that while risk inequality is indeed noticeable, there is less correlation across risk factors. This setting might seem counterintuitive, as high inequality implies that certain individuals face consistently high or low risks across all dimensions, which should be reflected in a higher dependence. Yet, it seems that dependence is determined by those in the middle of the average risk distribution, who seem to experience high exposure in some dimensions while remaining almost unaffected in others. This mixed pattern complicates policy responses, because it becomes more difficult to pinpoint and address moderate-risk populations who may be vulnerable in specific ways.

Other areas also exhibit medium-high Gini values, but present relatively high dependence values, with all regions exceeding the average dependence value in Europe (0.12 points). This should be interpreted as risks being unevenly distributed, such that those who are highly exposed tend to be affected across multiple dimensions simultaneously. Conversely, those with low exposure values remain largely insulated from risks in all dimensions. This is the case of Slovakia (0.37 Gini points), Germany and Slovakia (over 0.35), Finland (around 0.33) and some Spanish region (where Gini ranges from 0.28 to 0.37 points). In contrast, there are regions with similar dependence value (over 0.12 points), but medium-low inequality level (below 0.30 Gini points). Portugal and France fall within this groups, where risks are more equally distributed; risks are not concentrated in a few hands, but there is still correlation across risk factors.

Note that some regions in Spain, France and, to a lower extent, Portugal and Finland exhibit moderate average risk inequality values (with Gini coefficients around 0.30) and medium dependence (with most values lying between 0.12 and 0.15), suggesting a blend of the previously mentioned dynamics. These regions do not really fit neatly into one category but instead show a combination of risk distribution and correlation patterns, requiring a more profound case-study approach, way beyond the extent of this paper.

Figure 13. Diagonal dependance and Gini

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

The different combinations of inequality and dependence categories highlight a substantial diversity in risk exposure across European countries, as visualized in Figure 13. Although no clear geographical pattern emerges, Eastern European countries, including the Czech Republic, Poland, Hungary, Latvia, Romania, Bulgaria, and Lithuania, tend to be characterized by both lower dependence levels and overall lower inequality values. Conversely, several Central and Western European countries, such as Austria, Belgium, and the Netherlands, display relatively high levels of both inequality and dependence. Other regions present a more mixed profile, with varying levels of inequality and dependence, often falling closer to the European average. One possible reason behind this variation may be the uneven interaction between the average exposure to risks and the distribution of socioeconomic factors, that may ultimately reflect differences in demographic or social composition across regions.

5.5 Cumulative exposure: individual analysis

With this idea in mind, we turn now to explore the relative importance of socioeconomic factors in explaining the variability in average risk using the conditional variable importance method described in Section 3.4.¹³ Unsurprisingly, household income emerges as the most salient socioeconomic factor in explaining average risk exposure to climate change across most countries, with the main exception being Italy and the Czech Republic, where age is the most important regressor, respectively accounting for 26% and 34% of the normalized variable importance. For most countries, income serves as a comprehensive proxy for a wide range of factors that influence both vulnerability and adaptive capacity. Higher-income households typically are endowed with better access to resources that mitigate climate risks, such as income to afford increasing energy or transport prices, adequately insulated housing, insurance, and better access to healthcare. Conversely, lower-income households tend to have fewer adaptive options and are often more exposed to environmental hazards due to their geographic location or limited financial buffers.

Figure 14. Relative importance of Income to explain Average Risk by Country

Source: Own elaboration, EU-SILC data. Note: Values as a share after aggregating all relative importance values. Italy has the lowest value (28%).

¹³ We have checked that our results remain largely unaffected when other definitions of risk exposure are used as a dependent.

Despite the dominant role of income, in Figure 14 we observe substantial cross-country variation in its relative contribution to explaining risk exposure. In countries like Austria, Cyprus, Netherlands, Sweden, Portugal, and Slovakia, household income explains more than 60% of the total normalized observed variability across all regressors. Excluding Italy, income still plays a significant role in the Czech Republic (24%) and Finland (29%).

Figure 15 presents the second most important regressor across countries. Income emerges as the second most important variable in the Czech Republic, while regional disparities are a key factor in Italy (22%).¹⁴ In the remaining countries, where income was the main factor, there are two key variables at play. The occupation is relevant in Denmark, Romania Luxembourg, Belgium, Estonia, Germany, and Sweden, explaining between 23% and 13% of the variace, potentially reflecting the role of the socioeconomic position. Age outstands in other parts, representing between 8% (Austria) and 27% (Finland) of total variable importance, possibly pointing to the age related exposure to health issues. Other regressors, such as gender, household tenure, country of birth and sector where individuals work seem to play a relatively small role.

Figure B7 in the Appendix shows that education disparities are more associated with average individual risk in the East: Romania (5.7%), Bulgaria (5.6%), Poland (5%) and Hungary (4.5%), while in other countries like Austria and Germany, their influence is minimal, accounting for less than 2% of variable importance. A similar pattern is observed for household size disparities (Figure B8), which are particularly relevant in Czech Republic, Italy and Romania (10%), with very low relevance in Sweden, Austria, Denmark and Belgium (less than 3%).

Figure 15. Second Most Important variable

Source: Own elaboration, EU-SILC data.

¹⁴ Note that the geographical disaggregation is not available in some countries well known to have a substantial geographical divide such as Germany.

Overall, our findings reveal significant country-specific variations in risk distribution, with no clear regional patterns emerging –either geographically or in relation to welfare state regimes. This points towards the need for a more nuanced, country-specific analysis to account for national contexts, climatic conditions, and socio-economic structures shaping risk exposure.

5.6 Vulnerable groups in Europe

The estimation of conditional inference regression trees (ctree), as introduced by Hothorn et al. (2006), enables the identification of particularly vulnerable groups based on their average exposure to risk. For each country, we estimate a ctree model to explain average risk as a function of the same socioeconomic characteristics used in Section 5.5: educational level, sex, country of birth, age, self-reported health status, household size, housing tenure, household income, and employment sector and occupation, which proxy the socioeconomic groups they belong to. To avoid overfitting, we apply a highly conservative stopping rule with a confidence level of 99.99% and a minimum of 1% of the total sample required in each terminal node. The result is a partition of the population in each country into groups, that ranges between only 4 in Luxembourg to 48 in the Netherlands, for a total of 465 groups. Group’s specific average risk is extremely variable ranging between 0.0037 to 0.6095. Figure 16 shows as an example the groups obtained for Sweden. At the extreme right, group 15 is made of individuals living in household with intermediate number of members (2 to 5) and high income with an average risk below 5%. At the other extreme individuals living alone or in large households with a low level of education and a very low level of income (their risk is above 30%).

Figure 16: ctree explaining risk variability in Sweden as between-group inequality

Source: Own elaboration, EU-SILC data.

Sweden is a good example not only because the relative simplicity of its tree makes the structure easy to interpret, but also because it reveals an important insight: despite Sweden being a country with relatively low average risk, it exhibits substantial internal variability. This pattern holds consistently across the sample. In fact, 89% of the total variance in expected risk is attributable to within-country differences, while only 11% is explained by between-country variation. Ctree for each country are available upon request.

Considering all trees and in particular focusing on groups at highest risk (those with an average risk above 0.36, a threshold equal to three times the average risk in the entire sample), we notice an overrepresentation of certain countries: Greece, Ireland, and Portugal in particular. In Greece, the groups most affected by risk include individuals reporting poor health, extremely low income, or a low level of education, taken together they are more than 8% of the Greek population. Similarly, in Portugal, the highest-risk groups are characterized by poor self-reported health, low income, and household sizes at both extremes (either one member or six or more). In Ireland, surprisingly, the individuals at highest risk are not older adults but males under the age of 29. In Romania, the two groups facing the most severe risks also report poor health. Romania stands out as having the groups with the highest overall risk (above 60%); these individuals are male, have low educational attainment, and report bad health conditions. Finally, in Germany, one group exceeds the risk threshold. These are males employed as Skilled Agricultural, Forestry and Fishery Workers or in elementary occupations, and are under the age of 59. This group faces a risk just barely above the 0.36 threshold.

Our evidence highlights that vulnerabilities in Europe are primarily driven by socioeconomic factors, especially household income, though significant variation exists across countries. This evidence suggests a limited direct impact of climate variables in determining cumulative risks in Europe. After all, our indicators are expected to be more sensitive to the economic consequences of climate change rather than to direct climatic conditions. This is partially confirmed by our later analysis. While income is the dominant predictor in most cases, other factors such as age, health, occupation, region of residence, and household size play crucial roles in specific national contexts. Importantly, the vast majority of risk variability occurs within countries. At the same time, the heterogeneity in types of risk, their predictors, and the socio-demographic characteristics of those most at risk suggests the need for targeted national and sub-national policies rather than broad continental approaches.

5.7 Future exposure under two scenarios

This section examines projected exposure to the seven dimensions analysed in 2050. Following the methodology outlined in Section 3, we estimate the probability of individuals being affected by each of these dimensions in the future, those with higher probabilities being the vulnerable.¹⁵

The projections for climate related dimensions (energy, transport and health) are estimated under two alternative climate and socioeconomic scenarios, additionally matching population projections.¹⁶ To facilitate comparability, we calculate the change in the share of exposed individuals compared to the present situation for both scenarios: SSP2-RCP4.5 and SSP4-RCP8.5. For instance, a value of 0.1 means that 10% more of the population is at risk in 2050. Figure 17 maps the results separately for each dimension, highlighting several key findings.

Overall, the relative changes remain mid-sized, suggesting gradual shifts rather than abrupt transformations. Excluding a few outliers discussed below, in absolute terms, changes move around 5% in most cases. Yet, looking at the relative changes (Appendix Figure B10), we observe that the share of individuals at risk more than doubles in some areas in some cases. Although these cases may represent extreme situations, even increasing the vulnerable population by half can pose significant challenges, especially in those areas where the initial levels of risk are higher.

While some degree of geographical heterogeneity is observed, the expected changes in the health dimensions appear more moderate. Cardiovascular issues are expected to rise between 4 and 5% in Cyprus, Greece, Luxemburg, and fall by 4% in East Austria, but the change is equal or below 2% in most areas under both future scenarios, the change being slightly larger in SSP5-RCP8.5. Romania represents the most striking case, with almost 8% more exposed individuals. We have checked that cardiovascular issues are concentrated among the very old people, namely those over 80. Population projections more than double their population share, leading to a larger exposure. Without considering population dynamics, the share of vulnerable individuals barely changes with respect to present values, suggesting the importance of adding both climatic and population trends together.

The share of the population affected by respiratory conditions is also projected to remain largely stable at the aggregate level, with the exceptions of Italy and to a lower extent, Spain, Portugal and the Nordic countries. Looking at the relative change, the affected population will grow by half or more in these areas, so health risks are rather alarming. Most remarkably, although in absolute terms the expected change is not particularly salient in Romania (around 5%), given its lower initial levels of exposed individuals, the share of at-risk population will more than double (Figure B10, potentially threatening the healthcare system. This finding may seem counterintuitive given the rapidly changing climate, yet several factors may explain the limited variations observed in health outcomes. First, substantial changes in health outcomes may require larger climate shocks or longer time horizons before their effects become apparent at the population level. Second, the level of granularity in the data may influence the observed patterns. In particular, the EHIS, which provides information on health outcomes, does not offer regional-level data, meaning that both historical climate analysis and projections rely on country-level climate data. This limitation may underestimate regional disparities in climate-induced health risks.

¹⁵ We ensure predicted risks match the original data by fixing each country's share of affected individuals to that in the auxiliary survey.

¹⁶ We have projected climatic variable under two scenarios without reweighting the population to isolate the effect of climate change. Results, available upon request, remain largely unchanged, and the geographical patterns holds. Overall, the change in affected populations is slightly smaller.

The most significant changes, with values going up to 20%, are observed in the energy- and transport-related risks, indicating a widespread increase in energy poverty across Europe. This larger effect may be related to the direct link between climate and temperature, whereby climate shifts result in more extreme weather conditions, raising the demand for heating, cooling, or private transport. The effects in relative terms are also more notable for these two risks; the percentage of the population suffering from energy and transport poverty is projected to double or even triple in certain areas.

In the case of energy poverty, marked rises are observed in the Czech Republic, Finland, Portugal, and Slovakia, with more moderate increases in Central Europe, and even declining exposure in parts of the Mediterranean. By contrast, transport poverty is projected to either decline or remain stable in Central-Northern Europe, while worsening in Southern regions, Ireland, and the Czech Republic. Both energy and transport poverty are expected to become more prevalent under the severe climate change scenario (SSP5-RCP8.5). Cyprus is a clear outlier: transport poverty is projected to grow by 20% under SSP2-RCP4.5, even rising 40% under the severe scenario. In relative terms, the increase is particularly pronounced, affecting the scale of the graph. In other countries, differences between scenarios are considerably smaller. These results reflect the combined effects of projected climate change, its relationship with climate-related hazards, and the socioeconomic profile of the most vulnerable populations. In the following sections we will focus on such individual characteristics.

Figure 17. Absolute change of climate risks under two scenarios: SSP2-RCP4.5 and SSP4-RCP8.5.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure 18. Absolute change of socioeconomic risks.

Deprivation 2050

Poverty 2050

Work intensity 2050

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

It is important to note that risks linked to socioeconomic conditions are not climate-dependent; thus, the results solely reflect risks under future population projections. As shown in Figure 18, the changes are minimal. The changes are also moderate in relative term, the values ranging from 0.1 to -0.2. While the share of deprived individuals increases (falls) by 1% in Bulgaria and Romania (northern Greece), most of the regions remain unchanged, with a tiny fall in South Spain and some French regions. The changes are slightly larger for poverty, particularly in Latvia and Estonia, where 4% and 2% more of the population are respectively poor in 2050. Although the rise is smaller – between 1% and 2%– poverty also worsens in Eastern countries such as Bulgaria, the Czech Republic, Lithuania, and Romania. Elsewhere, poverty levels remain stable or even fall, with reductions between 1% and 3% in certain Spanish, Italian, and Greek regions. The share of individuals living in households with very low work intensity decreases across all regions, except in Champagne-Ardenne (France), where it rises by less than 1%. The reduction is mild in general, moving around 1%, but reaches up to 3% in south Spain and Italy.

Given that these results only depend on population dynamics, cross-country differences are compositional. They reflect the interaction between currently socioeconomically vulnerable demographic groups and their relative share in the projected population. Among these dynamics, the projected old-age dependency ratio—which captures the proportion of individuals aged 65 and over relative to those of working age—is expected to rise across all Europe.¹⁷ These demographic shifts are reflected in Figure 19. For example, Bulgaria is projected to experience the largest increase in deprivation. According to Eurostat, 31% of individuals over 64 are deprived in Bulgaria in 2019, compared to approximately 20% among other age groups. An increasing share of older individuals is thus associated with worse future outcomes.¹⁸ Conversely, in Southern European countries, older people exhibit the lowest levels of poverty risk, and overall poverty levels are projected to decline in these regions.¹⁹

The point is clearer when considering very low work intensity. This indicator excludes households composed only of children, students under 25, and individuals aged 65 or over. Therefore, a higher projected share of people over 64 implies fewer working-age individuals at risk, leading to a larger projected decline in exposure to this dimension. Figure 19 illustrates this relationship. Mediterranean countries are expected to undergo significant population ageing, and these are also the countries where the prevalence of very low work intensity is projected to decline the most.

It is important to acknowledge that this framework does not capture behavioural responses, which could significantly influence these projections. Mitigation and adaptation strategies, whether implemented at the individual, community, or governmental level, are likely to play a crucial role in shaping future outcomes. Therefore, while our findings highlight small and moderate changes, depending on the area and dimension, the actual extent of these changes will depend on the policy landscape and adaptive capacity of different regions.

¹⁷ Eurostat. Projected old-age dependency ratio: <https://doi.org/10.2908/TPS00200>

¹⁸ Eurostat. Severe material deprivation rate by age and sex: https://doi.org/10.2908/ILC_MDDD11

¹⁹ Eurostat. At-risk-of-poverty rate of older people, by age and sex: <https://doi.org/10.2908/TESS1012>

Figure 19. Population aging and change in low work intensity.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

The combination of these changes determines the extent to which individuals are exposed to climate change. We begin exploring such compound effects by examining the geographical distribution of average risk in 2050. While the spatial pattern remains consistent across scenarios, with higher risks in South-East Europe, average risk levels increase in nearly all regions. Figure 20 presents results under SSP2-RCP4.5, used for illustration given their close similarity to SSP5-RCP8.5, which shows only slightly larger increases.²⁰ Risk particularly rises in Portugal, Italy, Spain, Romania and the Czech Republic, with average increases between 0.03 and 0.05 points. In contrast, it remains broadly stable in Central Europe and declines by 0.01 to 0.02 in the Netherlands, Slovenia, and several French regions.

To complement the analysis, we also examine the distribution of minimum and maximum risk levels, shown in Appendix Figure B9 for scenario SSP2-RCP4.5. Minimum risk remains unchanged or decreases across most regions. This is consistent with our population projections, which reflect an ageing demographic profile largely unaffected by low work intensity; one of the key drivers of risk at the lower end of the distribution. The most pronounced reductions, ranging from 0.01 to 0.02, are observed in Italy, Spain, Greece, Ireland and parts of France and Eastern Europe. As shown in Figure 18, risks associated with work intensity are indeed expected to decline most notably in the Mediterranean region.

²⁰ Results for SSP5-RCP8.5 are available upon request.

Maximum risk, by contrast, exhibits more substantial increases, rising in all regions except Slovenia. The most significant changes occur in Portugal and Romania, where average maximum risk increases by approximately 0.4 points, followed by Ireland, Cyprus, Spain, and Finland. These patterns align with the multidimensional shifts illustrated in Figure 19: cardiovascular risks intensify in Romania; respiratory conditions worsen in Italy, Romania and parts of Spain; energy poverty increases in Finland and Portugal; and transport poverty rises in the Mediterranean and Ireland. Overall, the dominant risk factor in each region remains broadly stable, with cardiovascular disease, energy and poverty continuing to shape individual risk profiles.

Figure 20. Average risk 2050: SSP2-RCP4.5.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Although average risk increases, this change is not solely driven by movements at the extremes of the distribution. It also reflects shifts in the prevalence and intensity of intermediate risk levels. With this compositional aspect in mind, we turn to the analysis of risk inequality, using the Gini coefficient of average risk. Figure 21 presents the results for SSP2-RCP4.5. Excluding Belgium, inequality increases across all regions, with particularly pronounced rises in Northern Italy, France and Eastern Sweden. As before, the geospatial pattern of inequality remains relatively stable. Risk inequality tends to be lower in South-East Europe, with the notable exceptions of Romania and Italy, which exhibit some of the highest levels. This pattern suggests a potential trade-off: regions with higher average risk tend to display lower inequality, indicating that exposure becomes more evenly distributed when a larger share of the population is affected. In fact, inequality is slightly lower under SSP5-RCP8.5, on average around 1 Gini point lower, while average risk is higher.

Another key dimension of the distributional analysis concerns dependence, which captures the extent to which individuals are simultaneously affected by multiple risks. Under scenario SSP2-RCP4.5, dependence is projected to decline across most European regions, suggesting that cumulative exposure may become less relevant in the future. Although dependence moderately increases in some areas—such as Northern Italy, the Czech Republic, Poland and Slovenia, with rises between 0.01 and 0.03 points—more substantial reductions are observed elsewhere, particularly in

Austria and Estonia, where declines reach up to 0.11 points. Despite this general downward trend, the spatial distribution remains uneven: relatively higher dependence persists in parts of Central and Nordic Europe, while the lowest levels are found in Eastern Europe and Portugal. The picture remains similar under SSP5-RCP8.5.

Figure 21. Gini in the average risk 2050: SSP2-RCP4.5.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure 22. Diagonal dependence 2050: SSP2-RCP4.5.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

We do not observe any clear spatial pattern; rather, it appears that the internal distribution of vulnerability within each country plays a central role in shaping future exposure, both in terms of levels and distributional matters. Overall, regions with higher average risks also tend to exhibit higher inequality, as a larger share of the population is affected in one dimension or another. However, dependence decreases, suggesting that risks are becoming more randomly distributed across individuals. From a policy perspective, this scenario presents greater complexity. A larger proportion of the population is expected to be exposed, particularly under the more severe climate change scenario, but with risks less concentrated among specific groups, making targeted policy interventions more challenging.

Figure 23: Most relevant factor to explain Future Average Risk by Country

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

We examine within-country variation in average risk levels to identify the sociodemographic factors that explain this heterogeneity. As shown in Figure 23, income emerges as the primary determinant in many countries under both climate scenarios, including in Italy, where it is currently less relevant. The relative importance of income moves between 20 and 50%, depending on the area. In countries where income does not play a dominant role, such as the Netherlands, Belgium, Germany, the Czech Republic, Finland, Ireland, Greece, Romania, Slovakia, and Slovenia, household size, age and sex account for a substantial share of the variation. These findings highlight the importance of demographic structures, particularly the vulnerability of older populations, who are more likely to live in small households and experience poorer health. Overall, income and demographic aging appear

to be key drivers of future climate-related risks, either by buffering households against adverse shocks or exacerbating existing vulnerabilities.²¹

A broader perspective emerges when examining the second most important factor, as it provides additional insight into the characteristics of the most vulnerable populations. Appendix Tables B6 and B7 report the contribution of all factors under SSP2-RCP4.5 and SSP5-RCP8.5, allowing for comparisons both within and across countries. Under SSP2-RCP4.5, the most relevant secondary factors are consistent across countries: age (Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Spain, Lithuania, Latvia, Poland, Slovakia), occupation (Austria, Bulgaria, Estonia, France, Hungary, Luxembourg, Portugal), income (Germany, Finland) and household size (Cyprus, Italy and Sweden). Although the relative importance of some factors shifts under SSP5-RCP8.5, the combination of income, age, occupation and household size, either as primary or secondary determinants, continues to explain a substantial share of future risks.

Notable exceptions also arise. Education plays a key role in Ireland, the Czech Republic and Romania, explaining 22%, 18% and 20% of the variance, respectively. It is also significant in Finland (18%), where it takes the third place after income and education, as each account for around 20% of the variation, emphasizing their joint relevance. Similarly, region and household size alternate as the second and third most important variables in Italy, depending on the scenario. The sector is key in Slovenia, accounting for close to 22% under SSP2-RCP4.5, alongside income. Note that the magnitude and relative importance of these variables can vary across contexts. In both Austria and Luxembourg, income explains over 40%, and while occupation ranks second in both, its contribution doubles, from 11% in Austria to 21% in Luxembourg.

Taken together, these results highlight the importance of considering the full composition of explanatory variables to understand the distribution of future climate-related risks. Equally important is the recognition of country-specific dynamics, which may shape vulnerability in distinct ways and warrant closer, context-sensitive analysis.

²¹ It is important to highlight that our demographic projection does not account for the possibility that future socioeconomic conditions, such as pension policies and wage trends, may favor older or younger individuals differently. This type of modeling was clearly outside the scope of our exercise. However, it is likely to introduce various distortions. In some Eastern European countries, younger individuals in the future may find themselves in better economic conditions than the elderly today. In contrast, in certain Western countries facing limited budgetary space and a stagnant economy, the opposite may be true.

6. Conclusions

In this study, we have developed a framework to assess the exposure of European citizens to various risks. While many risks, ranging from geopolitical instability to the transition toward a greener economy, could affect EU citizens, our analysis focused specifically on climate-related risks. These include cardiovascular and respiratory issues, as well as energy and transport poverty. We considered and modeled these risks as being directly impacted by climate variables.

In addition, we considered several socioeconomic conditions that are not directly affected by climate variables but have the potential to exacerbate or mitigate climatic impacts. These include the indicators used to assess the risk of poverty and social exclusion in Europe: individuals at risk of poverty, those who are severely materially and socially deprived, and those living in households with very low work intensity.

Our approach consisted of two main steps. First, we integrated multiple datasets—including the Household Budget Surveys, the European Health Interview Survey and EU-SILC—to estimate individuals' probability of being exposed to different climate-related risks and of being socioeconomically vulnerable. We then mapped the distribution of risks across European regions, identified key predictive factors, their concentration, and the extent of cumulative exposure.

Our findings reveal significant regional variation. In terms of the geographical distribution of average risks, exposure is most pronounced in the Mediterranean and Eastern Europe, particularly in Bulgaria. In contrast, parts of Flanders, areas of France, Northern Spain, and North-West Romania stand out for their lower risk levels. These differences are largely driven by the geographical distribution of maximum risk, the values being the largest in Mediterranean countries, the Baltic states, and other parts of Eastern Europe. While the relevance of specific risk dimensions varies across regions, cardiovascular risk, poverty, and both energy and transport insecurity consistently emerge as the most prominent.

The distributional analysis also reveals diverse regional patterns, with varying combinations of inequality and dependence observed in the distribution of risks. Most notably, we identify two contrasting groups of countries, each with distinct policy implications. On the one hand, countries such as Italy, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Poland, and Latvia exhibit both low inequality and low dependence values. In these areas, risks are more evenly distributed across individuals and largely uncorrelated across dimensions. While this may suggest a fairer distribution, it poses challenges for policymakers: if individuals facing high risk in one area are not affected in others, who should be prioritized? Which dimension of risk should receive greater attention?

On the other hand, countries such as Cyprus, Ireland, Belgium, Austria, and, to a lesser extent, the Netherlands display higher levels of both inequality and dependence. Here, risk exposure is not only more unevenly distributed but also tends to be concentrated among the same individuals. This polarization may facilitate the identification and targeting of the most vulnerable populations, yet it also signals that certain individuals are highly at risk.

The individual-level analysis provides relevant policy insights. Income emerges as the strongest predictor of average risk exposure in most countries, suggesting that income protection policies could be effective in mitigating climate-related vulnerabilities across multiple dimensions. Age is also an important factor in many countries, especially in Italy and the Czech Republic. These findings suggest that public health systems must go beyond treating existing conditions. A more proactive approach is needed, incorporating preventive health strategies before climate-related impacts further intensify. This could include early detection, health education, and infrastructure investments,

such as creating public green and fresh air spaces, to protect high-risk populations, especially the elderly. Further analysis indicates that most of the variability in exposure occurs within countries rather than between them. Yet, the characteristics of high-risk groups differ across states, so we call for the design of country-specific targeting mechanisms.

The second step of our analysis examined the relationship between climate data, such as temperature, precipitation, and extreme weather events, and risk exposure. We found some evidence of non-linear relationships. We then projected future risks using two approaches. First, we reweighted the population to account for demographic aging. Second, using the relationships described above, we projected future risks under two climate scenarios.

For risks directly influenced by climate variables, relative changes remain moderate, suggesting gradual rather than abrupt transformations. Excluding a few outliers, absolute changes in at-risk population move around 5% in most cases. The share of the population affected by respiratory and cardiovascular conditions is projected to remain largely stable at the aggregate level. The most pronounced changes—reaching up to 20%—are observed in the energy and transport dimensions, pointing to a widespread increase in fuel-related risks. Changes in socioeconomic conditions are minimal but reflect the potential effects of population aging. Yet, the effects in relative terms are worryingly noteworthy, especially for the last two risks. The percentage of the population suffering from energy and transport poverty is projected to more than double in certain areas, with the potential to add greater pressure on health care systems.

While the spatial pattern of risks remains broadly consistent across scenarios, with higher levels concentrated in South-East Europe, average risk levels are projected to rise in nearly all regions, especially in the severe climate change scenario. No clear cross-country spatial pattern emerges. Instead, the internal distribution of risks within each country appears to play a central role in shaping future exposure and the most vulnerable groups.

Several factors may explain the limited variations observed in our projections. First, significant shifts in health outcomes may require larger climate shocks or longer time horizons to become evident at the aggregate level. Second, data granularity imposes constraints on our estimates. The highest level of aggregation available from Eurostat is NUTS 2, with the EHIS not even providing regional information, limiting our ability to precisely capture climate-risk relationships and refine future projections.

Another key limitation is that our framework does not account for behavioral responses, which could significantly influence these projections. Adaptation and mitigation strategies at individual, community, and governmental levels will play a crucial role in shaping future outcomes. While our results indicate moderate shifts in risk exposure, actual impacts will ultimately depend on policy interventions and the adaptive capacity of different regions.

Given the absence of strong geographical patterns and the modest nature of projected changes, our findings emphasize the importance of country-specific analyses. Such approaches would allow for the use of higher-resolution data, the construction of targeted models, and the integration of behavioral dynamics and uncertainty factors, leading to a more precise understanding of climate-related vulnerabilities and better-informed policy responses.

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Technical Appendix A: Future climate projections

Reliable projections of weather variables from climate models are essential for assessing the potential impacts of future climate change. With different modelling groups around the world producing different climate projections, the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project, now in its 6th phase (CMIP6), provides a framework for climate model experiments. Besides coordinating modelling centres and ensuring comparability, it allows scientists to analyse, validate and improve their models (Eyring et al., 2016).

All models in CMIP6 follow the socioeconomic pathway-representative concentration pathway (SSP-RCPs) scenarios, which provide plausible descriptions of the future, based on socio-economic and emission scenarios of how global society grows and develops (O'Neill et al., 2016; Riahi et al. 2017). Using CMIP6 projections data, we build climate projection under two alternative futures: a moderate (SSP2-RCP4.5) and severe climate change scenario (SSP5-RCP8.5).

The CMIP6 models generate climate projections for each scenario, but it is crucial to adjust the variables to account for biases in the models, instead of relying on raw output for impact modelling. Since climate models are not perfect representations of reality, they often exhibit systematic differences between their simulations and observed data (Ho et al., 2012). Rather than comparing simulated future values with observed counterparts, we use the 'delta' change method (Navarro-Racines, et al, 2020).

Namely, we compute the differences between the simulated historic and future climate (Eq. 1), i.e., anomaly, and add it to the observed historical climate data (Eq. 2).

$$\Delta X_i = X_{Fi} - X_{Si} \quad (1)$$

$$X_{Fi} = X_{Hi} - \Delta X_i \quad (2)$$

The anomaly for each climate variable i (ΔX_i) is estimated comparing the 20-year mean (2040-2059) of the future values (X_{Fi}) with the 20-year mean (1994-2014) simulated historical values (X_{Si}) for each CMIP6 model.²² The future projection (X_{Fi}) is obtained by adding the anomaly to the historical climatology (1995-2014), computed using ERA5 reanalysis data.

We use relative changes for precipitation to avoid obtaining negative values when applying the anomaly to observed historical precipitation. Following Navarro-Racines, et al. (2020) we make two adjustments. First, we prevent indetermination in Eq. 3 by setting a threshold of 0.1mm yearly rain for simulated historical and future values. Second, we truncate the top 2% of anomaly values to the 98th percentile value for each anomaly gridded dataset to avoid unrealistic high precipitation projections.

²² World Bank (2024) lists the models. We use ensemble values from each of the models in the collection, and take the median across the individual model. This leads to more robust projections than those produced by any individual model.

Formally:

$$\Delta X_{pr} = \frac{X_{Fpr} - X_{Spr}}{X_{Spr}} \quad (3)$$

$$X_{Fpr} = X_{Hi} * (1 + \Delta X_{pr}) \quad (4)$$

Future climate projections are derived at the grid level. We get population weighted NUTS climate projections by using gridded SSP-consistent population projections (Jones and O'Neill, 2016). We apply the delta change method to obtain such projections. For each scenario (SSP2 and SSP5), the anomaly is calculated comparing the projected population (2040-2059) with the population in the historical reference period (1995-2014). The CCKP provides both, the projections and the historical collections, which requires no further harmonization. The difference is then added to the 2015 GHS-POP gridded population (see Data section).

Results Appendix B

Table B1. Energy and transport vulnerability by country in 2020.

Country	Energy 10	Energy 2m	Energy lihc	Transport 10	Transport 2m	Transport lihc
AT	4.00	11.80	14.63	4.78	13.13	8.19
BE	4.36	11.17	13.99	1.09	8.03	6.05
BG	32.51	12.60	17.12	9.53	14.49	3.07
CY	3.05	10.65	13.59	19.79	8.88	12.90
CZ	45.54	13.04		12.03	15.28	
DE	8.92	11.83	13.88	4.10	11.06	8.36
DK	10.65	17.24	12.82	0.61	10.45	5.22
EE	10.26	15.02	14.22	6.16	7.35	4.15
EL	15.08	10.30	17.56	7.52	11.65	10.03
ES	4.15	13.09	18.16	9.44	13.62	9.71
FI	4.00	21.01	7.37	7.32	10.13	5.10
FR	3.29	11.23	13.61	10.09	10.48	8.53
HU	9.44	7.07	15.06	5.44	11.99	5.50
IE	5.64	12.38	14.52	7.71	14.34	10.08
IT	11.29	12.37		11.38	9.83	
LT	20.36	11.76	16.18	6.25	4.67	2.27
LU	0.80	12.31	15.69	1.48	14.29	10.02
LV	22.95	8.23	15.23	14.86	12.19	3.13
NL	2.47	7.23	11.20	1.77	14.45	5.45
PL	27.13	13.81	16.88	9.50	12.93	8.97
PT	14.03	13.05	18.38	22.19	14.41	12.86
RO	28.10	14.69	15.98	6.13	8.99	3.12
SE	4.67	20.47	7.23	11.43	11.52	8.09

SI	13.21	9.48	13.18	16.51	12.57	7.72
SK	22.01	7.28	13.44	4.25	13.97	4.94

Source: Own calculation based on HBS 2020. HBS 2015 for IE, PL, RO, SE, and PT.

Table B2. Individuals with cardiovascular and respirators problems in 2019

Country	Cardio	Respiratory	Country	Cardio	Respiratory	Country	Cardio	Respiratory
AT	23,86	7,66	LV	33,31	6,37	IE	13,20	8,85
BE	18,61	8,48	MT	19,67	6,39	IS	27,13	12,73
BG	31,97	4,76	PL	29,14	5,88	IT	21,99	7,64
CY	20,54	5,75	RO	16,98	2,42	LT	32,17	8,44
CZ	28,14	6,12	SI	27,39	7,24	LU	16,93	9,76
EE	25,75	5,81	SK	30,91	5,85	NL	18,19	9,67
EL	22,56	4,85	DE	28,56	11,43	NO	16,81	9,41
ES	20,20	6,01	DK	20,65	9,57	PT	28,61	9,17
FR	16,45	12,40	FI	29,76	11,51	SE	19,55	8,63
HU	33,00	7,85	HR	40,55	7,93	UK	18,50	11,10

Source: EHIS wave 3. Wave 2 for FR and UK.

Table B3. AROPE population in 2019: Individuals in very low work intensity households, facing severe deprivation and poverty risk

Country	Work Intensity	Deprivation	Poverty	Country	Work Intensity	Deprivation	Poverty
AT	0.08	0.02	0.13	IE	0.13	0.05	0.13
BE	0.13	0.04	0.14	IT	0.11	0.08	0.19
BG	0.09	0.21	0.22	LT	0.08	0.1	0.2
CH	0.06	0.02	0.16	LU	0.08	0.01	0.16
CY	0.07	0.08	0.14	LV	0.08	0.08	0.25
CZ	0.04	0.03	0.1	MT	0.05	0.03	0.16
DE	0.08	0.03	0.15	NL	0.1	0.02	0.13
DK	0.11	0.03	0.13	NO	0.09	0.02	0.12
EE	0.06	0.03	0.23	PL	0.05	0.04	0.16
EL	0.16	0.16	0.17	PT	0.07	0.06	0.17
ES	0.12	0.04	0.19	RO	0.06	0.14	0.22
FI	0.11	0.02	0.12	SE	0.08	0.01	0.16
FR	0.08	0.05	0.13	SI	0.06	0.03	0.12
HU	0.05	0.08	0.12	SK	0.06	0.08	0.1

Source: EUSILC 2019.

Table B4. Average Marginal effects: climate and vulnerability

	(1)	(2)	(4)	(5)
	Energy (LIHC)	Transport (2M)	Respiratory	Cardiovascular
tas (temp)		0.0009693*** (0.0002871)		
pr	-0.0000031 (0.0000024)	-0.0000115*** (0.00000199)		
cdd	0.0000650*** (0.0000029)			
hdd	0.0000033*** (0.000001)			
hd35				-0.006478*** (0.000809)
hd30				
fd			-0.000472*** (0.0000624)	
r20mm			0.0016251*** (0.0004411)	0.003741*** (0.0005589)
N (Obs.)	1499769	1667018	782781	785190
McFadden R ²	0.062	0.021	0.081	0.281

Note: Standard errors are reported in parentheses below the coefficients together with the statistical significance of the effect (p < 0.01 for ***, p < 0.05 for **, p < 0.1 for *).

Table B5. Average Marginal effects (climate and vulnerability): robustness

	Energy		Transport	
	2M	10	LIHC	10
cdd65	0.000061*** (0.0000029)	0.0000629*** (0.0000033)		
hdd65	0.0000067*** (0.0000007)	0.0000065*** (0.000001)		
pr	-0.0000044** (0.000002)	0.0000389*** (0.0000023)	-0.000022*** (0.0000016)	-0.0000137*** (0.0000016)
tas (temp)			0.0026325*** (0.00023002)	0.0015406*** (0.000231)
Observations	1667018	1667018	1499769	1667018
McFadden R ²	0.042	0.152	0.057	0.076

Note: Standard errors are reported in parentheses below the coefficients together with the statistical significance of the effect (p < 0.01 for ***, p < 0.05 for **, p < 0.1 for *)

Figure B1. Historic climate and projection: very hot days and heavy precipitation days.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure B2. Fitted values cardiovascular and respiratory problem: very hot and frost days.

Source: World Bank Climate Change Knowledge Portal & EHIS.

Figure B3. Average lowest risk by region.

Lowest risk

Source: Own elaboration, data from EU-SILC.

Figure B4. Average highest risk by region.

Highest risk

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure B5. Average risk by dimension and region.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure B6. Average risk of climatic risks

Average risk

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure B7. Relative Importance of Education

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure B8. Relative Importance of Household Size

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure B9. Change in average lowest and highest risk: SSP2-RCP4.5.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.1.

Figure B10. Relative change of exposure under two scenarios: SSP2-RCP4.5 and SSP4-RCP8.5.

Source: Own elaboration from surveys listed in section 4.

Table B6. Relative importance of factors: SSP2-RCP4.5

Country	Region	Education	Sex	Country of birth	Age	Household size	House tenure	Income	Sector	Occupation
AT	0.003	0.024	0.004	0.048	0.098	0.052	0.029	0.561	0.062	0.118
BE	0.024	0.022	0.002	0.015	0.205	0.335	0.010	0.158	0.082	0.148
BG	0.014	0.123	0.007	0.000	0.116	0.072	0.003	0.450	0.059	0.156
CY	0.000	0.127	0.017	0.013	0.055	0.213	0.022	0.317	0.083	0.154
CZ	0.010	0.184	0.002	0.004	0.099	0.462	0.002	0.061	0.056	0.119
DE	0.000	0.027	0.006	0.003	0.190	0.351	0.002	0.261	0.045	0.116
DK	0.000	0.045	-0.001	0.021	0.210	0.074	0.012	0.392	0.101	0.147
EE	0.000	0.066	0.001	0.030	0.125	0.052	0.001	0.509	0.071	0.147
EL	0.005	0.136	0.000	0.008	0.218	0.297	0.004	0.185	0.053	0.096
ES	0.020	0.048	-0.003	0.016	0.159	0.052	0.008	0.499	0.057	0.145
FI	0.004	0.182	0.005	0.008	0.092	0.361	0.008	0.228	0.034	0.079
FR	-0.017	0.073	-0.007	0.020	0.127	0.049	0.040	0.421	0.070	0.225
HU	0.009	0.093	0.006	0.001	0.140	0.118	0.001	0.367	0.087	0.178
IE	0.000	0.230	0.124	0.001	0.391	0.054	0.009	0.100	0.046	0.045

IT	0.113	0.036	-0.002	0.020	0.102	0.161	0.004	0.377	0.068	0.121
LT	0.000	0.129	0.032	0.008	0.190	0.093	0.001	0.290	0.094	0.164
LU	0.000	0.079	0.006	0.054	0.067	0.020	0.029	0.441	0.094	0.210
LV	0.000	0.063	-0.001	0.026	0.155	0.067	0.002	0.479	0.061	0.148
NL	0.000	0.050	0.003	0.019	0.215	0.346	0.013	0.127	0.129	0.099
PL	0.013	0.075	-0.002	0.004	0.193	0.058	0.002	0.454	0.078	0.125
PT	0.009	0.101	0.018	0.008	0.112	0.090	0.006	0.423	0.050	0.183
RO	-0.001	0.208	0.338	0.000	0.118	0.179	0.001	0.062	0.032	0.061
SE	0.002	0.187	0.002	0.021	0.047	0.318	0.007	0.335	0.020	0.061
SI	0.000	0.070	0.004	0.030	0.256	0.081	0.006	0.204	0.220	0.131
SK	0.000	0.137	0.001	0.002	0.153	0.098	0.001	0.413	0.071	0.125

Table B7. Relative importance of factors: SSP5-RCP8.5

Country	Region	Education	Sex	Country of birth	Age	Household size	House tenure	Income	Sector	Occupation
AT	0.004	0.023	0.005	0.048	0.097	0.052	0.031	0.564	0.053	0.124
BE	0.049	0.033	0.000	0.023	0.242	0.054	0.016	0.333	0.098	0.152
BG	0.014	0.117	0.007	0.000	0.113	0.077	0.004	0.443	0.059	0.165
CY	0.000	0.170	0.026	0.017	0.071	0.085	0.019	0.360	0.065	0.187
CZ	0.013	0.187	0.005	0.003	0.099	0.461	0.003	0.057	0.064	0.107
DE	0.000	0.020	0.005	0.003	0.158	0.054	-0.001	0.501	0.054	0.208
DK	0.000	0.042	0.002	0.019	0.226	0.058	0.014	0.412	0.078	0.150
EE	0.000	0.070	0.003	0.027	0.115	0.050	0.002	0.514	0.077	0.142
EL	0.009	0.231	0.003	0.006	0.117	0.290	0.003	0.145	0.070	0.127
ES	0.013	0.052	-0.001	0.015	0.159	0.054	0.008	0.505	0.071	0.125
FI	0.005	0.193	0.020	0.009	0.150	0.339	0.009	0.191	0.022	0.062
FR	-0.001	0.084	-0.002	0.018	0.119	0.042	0.038	0.413	0.076	0.214
HU	0.010	0.085	0.001	0.000	0.147	0.105	0.003	0.382	0.089	0.177
IE	0.000	0.231	0.123	0.002	0.395	0.052	0.009	0.099	0.045	0.044

IT	0.133	0.030	-0.002	0.020	0.095	0.122	0.007	0.423	0.063	0.110
LT	0.000	0.119	0.030	0.007	0.185	0.108	0.001	0.302	0.074	0.174
LU	0.000	0.068	0.017	0.057	0.085	0.032	0.024	0.418	0.086	0.214
LV	0.000	0.059	0.000	0.027	0.153	0.067	0.002	0.483	0.055	0.155
NL	0.000	0.035	0.088	0.006	0.375	0.303	0.009	0.046	0.059	0.080
PL	0.013	0.074	-0.001	0.006	0.192	0.059	0.002	0.450	0.079	0.125
PT	0.001	0.086	0.012	0.008	0.107	0.097	0.008	0.440	0.061	0.180
RO	-0.002	0.219	0.337	0.000	0.111	0.225	0.000	0.040	0.020	0.049
SE	0.005	0.180	0.002	0.021	0.045	0.324	0.009	0.335	0.025	0.053
SI	0.000	0.063	0.004	0.031	0.195	0.077	0.004	0.210	0.282	0.135
SK	0.000	0.111	0.000	0.001	0.119	0.068	0.001	0.488	0.100	0.112

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